

had cases in which the sinus was completely obliterated by clot, and he can not say that if the patient gets well there is no clot.

DR. OPPENHEIMER, continuing the discussion, in answer to Dr. Smith's question, said that he had been particularly cautious, by reason of these controversies, not to be too enthusiastic. Many cases had been admitted to the hospital with but fewest of otitic symptoms, with suggestions of typhoid fever possibly, with no symptoms of mastoiditis, but with a positive blood culture. He had been extremely cautious in saying that he was dealing with infectious phlebitis, and had deferred operating until all other possible causes had been ruled out. Invariably they had found a thrombotic condition in the sinus.

Answering a question by Dr. George L. Richards as to whether all his ninety or ninety-five cases were operated upon, he said they were.

DR. WENDELL C. PHILLIPS verified Dr. Day's statements. He had been struck, years ago, in operative surgery on the ear, to find occasionally an obliterated sinus from an old sinus thrombosis.

DR. JOHN A. THOMPSON recalled having treated a brother laryngologist for suppurative ethmoiditis. He developed an abscess in the big toe which was opened under antiseptic precautions, and examination of the pus revealed the presence of streptococci. The nasal sinuses are sometimes at fault in bacteremia.

DR. SHEPPARD, in closing the discussion, said he simply reported four cases as a part of a group of cases of bacteremia, many of the group being cases which had been operated upon. Regarding the tying of the jugular, he had rather settled down to the rules of not tying it if there is a reasonably good return-flow from the bulb. Should there be no return flow he waited a day or two and then tied off the jugular. It was probably true, as Dr. Richardson suggested, that he was fortunate in not having bad results. Possibly more than simple good fortune is indicated by the fact that the cases referred to were selected from perhaps fifty or more cases of bacteremia, of which he had kept careful records, and of which twenty-five at least had not been operated upon. Dr. Thompson referred to other sources of bacteremia. This fact needs to be kept in mind. He very decidedly does not advocate operating upon all cases of bacteremia. Dr. Oppenheimer spoke of his cases as being cases of suppurative otitis. Three of the cases reported in the paper were non-suppurative otitis. He questions the necessity of operating upon all these cases if they are properly watched, especially if in conjunction with a practical bacteriologist. He thinks that more extensive observations would ultimately teach in which cases to operate and in which surgical intervention is not necessary.

Treatment of Purulent Cerebrospinal Meningitis. DR. WILLIAM SOHMER BRYANT, New York. The object of this communication is to apply the experience of an unusually successful case to the management of this infection.

The treatment of purulent septic meningitis consists of (1) treatment for relief of the intra-cranial pressure; (2) treatment of the toxemia; (3) treatment of the focal infection. The goal of the treatment is the control of intra-cranial pressure and toxemia, and the treatment should, there-

fore, be symptomatically directed against these two means of fatal terminations of the disease.

The following case, showing recovery from purulent streptococcic cerebrospinal meningitis, was offered: The patient, male, 22 years of age, had symptoms of rapidly increasing coma, neuro-muscular signs of meningitis, rigidity of neck, choked discs, and purulent otitis media and mastoiditis. Temperature, 102.5°; pulse, 40. Spinal fluid contained cocci in pairs and short chains, and pus. Decompression at once removed the mental symptoms. Mastoid operation, hypodermoclysis, enemata, saline solution by mouth, and solution of magnesium sulphate by mouth. On the seventh day following decompression, all signs of meningitis had disappeared. Patient died 188 days after the decompression operation, from toxemia caused by the repeated secondary infection of the decompression wound.

From this case the following conclusions are reached: "The combination of our experiences as otologists with the experience of the obstetrician makes the outlook for successful treatment of streptococcic meningitis appear much brighter than it has previously appeared. Oto-laryngologists should get as good results in cerebrospinal meningitis as the obstetrician obtains with puerperal sepsis cases. Although the surgeon can readily protect the patient from death by intra-cranial pressure, the management of the sepsis is quite another problem. This problem of sepsis has received more attention from the obstetrician than from any other medical group or specialty. The treatment should be focused on decompression, local and systemic drainage, administration of magnesium sulphate, and stimulating general hygiene."

Observation of Nystagmus Through the Closed Eyelids. DR. EDMUND PRINCE FOWLER, New York City.

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DISCUSSION.

DR. ARTHUR B. DUEL thought Dr. Fowler had presented a very ingenious method of making permanent records of ocular phenomena in vestibular nystagmus. He did not think such observations necessary to diagnosis, but when the apparatus was perfected the records, for those who understood them, would be useful in reporting cases. The tracings of nystagmus would leave no doubt of its presence. When one must depend upon the house-staff to report cases that arrived during one's absence, these tracings could be made and put into the records for subsequent study.

DR. FOWLER, in closing the discussion, said patients did not notice as much vertigo with rotation or following caloric reactions with the eyelids closed as they did with them open. For instance, one could produce nystagmic movements of the eyes with caloric stimulations and stop before the vertigo came on. Irrigation usually makes patients deathly ill and it surely is a great advantage to be able to avoid this annoying feature of the labyrinth tests. In many neurasthenics the rotation tests show nothing on account of the incessant blinking and rolling of the eyes around and about. If the lids are closed some approximation of the duration of the nystagmus may be ascertained.